

Coherent Quantum Feedback Control of a BEC Under Communication Constraints: Proposed Simulation and Analytical Study

Aman Chawla

January 24, 2025

Abstract

BEC is a unique semiclassical/quantum system. We work with its simulations. The goal is to induce BEC formation using external controls under communication constraints. This proposal will test anytime information concepts in a quantum setting.

In this note the authors propose to control a BEC - induce solitons [1] in it - using coherent [2] or semiclassical control in the presence of a communication channel [3, 4, 5]. Our first step is to replicate the theorem on tracking an unstable stochastic process over a classical channel in the quantum setting, in order to understand the mechanics. The next step is to implement the BEC using a Gross-Pitaevskii Equation simulation. Then we will use the external potential term to control the BEC soliton evolution. The signals or commands to the external potential term will be generated via a closed-loop controller which will interface with the plant via the communication channel. In the final step both the plant and the channel will be fully quantized. This study as proposed, will help in testing the limits of anytime information theory in the quantum or semi-classical domain. Post-simulation an analytical study will be taken up to explore the fundamental limits.

References

- [1] Vyacheslav A Trofimov and Artem V Rozantsev. 2d soliton formation of bec at its interaction with external potential. In *Photonic Fiber and Crystal Devices: Advances in Materials and Innovations in Device Applications VI*, volume 8497, pages 84–96. SPIE, 2012.
- [2] Seth Lloyd. Coherent quantum feedback. *Physical Review A*, 62(2):022108, 2000.
- [3] Sekhar Tatikonda and Sanjoy Mitter. Control under communication constraints. *IEEE Transactions on automatic control*, 49(7):1056–1068, 2004.

- [4] Sekhar Tatikonda and Sanjoy Mitter. The capacity of channels with feedback. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 55(1):323–349, 2008.
- [5] Anant Sahai and Sanjoy Mitter. The necessity and sufficiency of anytime capacity for stabilization of a linear system over a noisy communication link - Part I: Scalar systems. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 52(8):3369–3395, 2006.